

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Telling from Afar: The Politics of Voice in Diasporic Testimonio

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ABSTRACT

Politics and emerging ideologies are closely related to culture, and they have also influenced both Literature and criticism. Politics, culture, history, and ideology, which are closely intertwined, have formed a distinct area of research and have profoundly influenced critical thought. In Literature, it has had a profound influence on the creation of literature, and correspondingly, has given rise to a new branch of Literary Criticism that considers culture as a source of literary analysis. The new generation of scholars and intellectuals has been influenced by popular music, new research in science and technology, rapid globalisation, and industrial growth. The cultures of the new generation are distinct from those of the past, which were largely shaped by books. Modern artists, writers, and critics owe a great deal to the new "visual and aural culture" for shaping their worldviews and cultural standards. This generation is proud of how well it has absorbed these "cultural influences" from previous generations. The popular new culture has captivated even the Previous Generation's Scholars and Intellectuals. The word "reading" is being applied in its widest meaning. Distinguishing between reading and theory is essential. Theorising and reading, though, go hand in

hand. Both reading acts and the theory develop out of one another. Two have never been able to get along.

Keywords: politics; culture; new culture; history; ideology

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Introduction

One of the Consequences of the invasion of the new culture has been the weakening of Literature's position, which has always occupied a central place in cultural discourse. Now, Literature does not enjoy a pivotal position in Cultural issues. It is only one symptom of culture. Scientists in the social sciences and those in the humanities have closed the gap between their disciplines. Scholars in the humanities and anthropology live on a dynamic of mutual exchange. This is the first step of a multidisciplinary investigation. Although all Transnationals live in a globalised world, not all diasporas can be classified as such. The difference between transnationalism, a way of life, and diaspora, about leaving, is stark. Contrast this with transnational groups, which form through voluntary movement rather than forced migration, such as diasporas.

It is critical to study and understand the components of diasporic individuals' different mentalities. The seven elements that make up the Diasporic Consciousness are as follows: Embedding, A Sense of Belonging, Memory, Return, Strangeness, Desire to Integrate, Transcience, Desire for Permanence. Some of the characteristics of diasporic Literature are alienation, adoption, assimilation, depression, discontentment, death, nostalgia, marginalisation, readjustment, and rootlessness. It is difficult to bridge the gap between one's "home" culture and one's "world" culture, and the boundaries between the two are often fraught with tension. Themes, styles, modes, characters, and approaches in Literature from the diaspora provide fertile ground for critical inquiry.

In Latin, "testimonio" means "witness narrative," and this is where the term "testimonial literature" gets its start. Survivors of political violence, such as torture, genocide, or war, share their stories in testimonios. Some survivors wish to document their sufferings—not necessarily every time, but frequently enough. No narrative is better than any other, and there is no right or wrong way to tell or listen to a tale. The

offering of a witness also does not guarantee an easy solution. According to testimonialists, Testimonios provides a platform for the silent. Testimonios will highlight the significant fight across many disciplines and institutions to amplify the voices of those silenced in places affected by political violence.

A Testimonio is challenging to categorise; the word Testimonio comprises everything, i.e., when a person who is victimised by any oppressive force registers their sufferings or traumatic experiences, or those of their communities. Testimonial Literature is said to be a powerful tool for Subalterns because they are misrepresented, and through Testimonios, their true plight is brought to light.

Testimonial Literature enables readers to raise crucial questions about the past and how it comes down to the Present, and it also showcases the various transmissions. The main aim of the Testimonial Literature is to unmask Western Hegemony. On the other hand, there was a heated argument that the Testimonios and the Autobiographies go hand in hand, which is not true. In Autobiographies, the Self becomes important, whereas in Testimonios, the collective Self becomes important. Nowadays, in the Dalit Testimonios, the Individual Self and the Collective Self are inseparable. It is not fair to say that the Autobiographies and the Testimonios are similar.

In Testimonios, the shocking evils of society are brought out, whereas in Autobiographies, it is a celebration of the Self. The Individual is highlighted in the Autobiographies, whereas in the Testimonial Literature the Individual alone is not given importance, as s/he is seen as part of the oppressed people. It is noteworthy that Testimonial Literature serves as a forum for participation not only for Latin American Women but also for underprivileged individuals who lack access to the written word.

Periphery or marginalised peoples are creating testimonies as a form of resistance to colonialism. The narrative has become more prominent in Testimonios. It should be mentioned that political ambitions drive the process of native hybridisation and mirror a radicalisation of awareness. Additionally, testimonios document the trauma. The submission of oppressed people to the ruling classes gave rise to testimonial literature. The evolution of testimonial literature has revealed oppression across many social contexts and influenced diverse paths of thought. This dissertation highlights the underrepresented voices of the people and demonstrates how government agencies are involved in subversive activities.

In academia, 'Diaspora' and 'Testimonial Literature' are considered to be two ends of a spectrum, both different and irreconcilable. However, Diaspora communities may express their rootlessness through Testimonial Literature. The term 'Diasporic Testimonio' foregrounds the hidden voices of people who are either exiles or treated as exiles in their own homeland. This dissertation demonstrates a meaningful interface between Diasporic Literature and Testimonial Literature. Displacement, Dislocation, and Disjunction are the keywords in Diasporic Literature. Wherever there is displacement & dislocation, and disjunction, conflict occurs, which ends in the production of Testimonios.

For both theoretical discussions, the word "conflict" is crucial. The existence of conflict brings the contextualisations of both theories into harmony. The victims' voices, as shown in Diasporic Testimonio, have been silenced as a result of politics. They are not even allowed to be acknowledged for what they truly are: human. As shown in Diasporic Testimonios, victims are compelled to embark on new routes after losing their origins and becoming homeless. As hegemonic structures are built, their physical environment becomes even more repressive.

Diasporic Testimonio texts are prevalent in Sri Lankan, Tribal, and Israeli-Palestinian Literature. Through these texts, Diasporic Testimonio has the power to alter the meanings people derive from their experiences of political violence; for this reason, Diasporic Testimonio texts are valuable. Others at times see the Diasporic Testimonio as problematic or even dangerous. Multiple disciplines and institutions concerned with addressing the consequences of Political violence claim that Diasporic Testimonial Literature is a powerful tool for them.

There are several ways to interpret Diasporic Testimonio, including contextualisation, reductionism, objectification, and personalisation. It is clear from this dissertation that the author is looking forward to writing Diasporic Testimonios, in which they describe the damage and losses resulting from political violence. Stories from the diaspora have a lasting influence because they share inspiring and meaningful experiences.

Renowned Tamil poet Dr Rudhramoorthy Cheran. It is hardly surprising that his childhood experiences in Jaffna, Northern Sri Lanka, during the Civil War and his exposure to large-scale State Terrorism would inform his poetry. Poetically, Cheran is most concerned with issues of race and nationality. His anthology, *A Second Sunrise*, details the destruction of historical records. Thousands of Tamils were killed in the ensuing massacres. Both sides harassed Cheran since he refused to join either of the

competing militant groups there. Histories are claimed to be hinted at in Cheran's poetry, which acts as a societal documentary. That is why his poetry is perfect for a book called Diasporic Testimonio.

The poems of Mohamed Darwish, collected in *Diasporic Testimonios*, function as social documentaries. He is often regarded as Palestine's greatest poet. His poetry gives voice to the Palestinian people who have been silenced for too long, and his words represent the shared commitment to their homelands that everyone should share. By analysing the poems of Mohamed Darwish, we can see how the *Diasporic Testimonio* he represents encompasses a wide range of emotions, from numbness and disinterest to fear and trepidation to melancholy and anguish to hopelessness and projection. These countries have the most influence.

Many diasporic accounts credit indigenous texts for sparking their own ideas and beliefs. Specific indigenous communities view the term "development" with disdain. Since tribal people adhere to a worldview that sees a close relationship between all living things and God, they have faith in humans' ability to spell and understand reality accurately. The world is more sacred to them than secular; they let their emotions dictate their decisions rather than reason, and they perceive time as subjective rather than objective. G.N. Devy, who is frequently considered the gold standard of tribal Literature, describes in detail the various ways in which tribal life is unique. Many poems by indigenous peoples address migration. Some of the tribal poetry manages to hold on to the shared sorrow, uprooting, and tragedy. Their hope for a brighter future for their nation stems from their ability to remember the past. Concurrently, institutional knowledge has been and will be marginalised.

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